

MOLECULAR LEVEL INTERACTIONS IN CARBON NANOTUBE YARN – EPOXY MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Future high performance structural and multifunctional composites may utilize continuous carbon nanotube reinforcements. The nano-scale interactions between carbon nanotubes and epoxy macromolecules in such composites open new areas of research and technology. Tensile mechanical tests and Dynamic Mechanical Analysis are used here for gaining an initial understanding of such interactions and explaining some unusual mechanical properties on the studied nanocomposites.

Keywords: Carbon Nanotube, Nanocomposite, Epoxy Matrix, Textile Reinforcement, Mechanical Properties

INTRODUCTION

The properties inherent to carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have lead many to believe that they may be the building blocks for future composite products that may some day overtake carbon fiber as the pre-eminent structural reinforcement material. The route to producing these superior composites is still to be determined, however, there is increasing interest in producing aligned, continuous length yarns or fibers from CNTs with extremely high aspect ratios. This route is favoured by many composite engineers and scientists for four primary reasons: (1) The volume fraction of oriented CNTs is much higher than that typically obtained by mixing or dispersing individual nanotubes in polymer matrices. (2) CNT length to diameter ratios can be extremely high. (3) The CNTs within the fibers can have a high degree of alignment which is inherent to their production method. (4) Textile reinforcements are useful when more than one CNT orientation is desired, and those can be easily created by traditional textile and composite machinery to provide the desired CNT orientations. The study conducted in this paper provides first insight into the matrix – reinforcement interactions that occur in textile nanocomposites. The knowledge of these interactions is fundamental to the development of future composites of this type. As mechanical testing has shown, their properties may be very surprising and truly unprecedented [1].

Carbon nanotube yarns and fibers are produced using three different methods that give a similar end product. The term CNT yarns is commonly used when the resulting fiber has a twisted morphology, which is similar to traditional textile yarns in appearance. The term CNT fiber is more commonly used when the CNTs have an orientation which is close to the fiber axis. Product made from acid solution spinning [2] and from

drawing coagulated CNTs from an aerogel in a CVD furnace [3] fall into the fiber category because they contain minimal twist and their average orientation is parallel to the fiber direction. The yarns used in this study were made by the draw twist method developed in [4]. Other groups have also been concurrently developing and improving this technology [5,6].

The novelty and importance of studying the behaviour of CNT yarn composites comes from the fact that their hierarchical morphology is very different, and much more complex, than traditional microstructure of composites reinforced with micro-scale diameter fibers. Accordingly, their internal load transfer mechanisms and the resulting properties appear very different. Although CNT yarns fabricated and studied in [1] are densely packed, there is still about 60% free volume among the CNTs remaining. Ideally, all of that can be infiltrated by a polymer resin. The free spaces among CNTs, although they are on the scale of tens of nanometers, are larger than typical transverse dimensions of the resin macromolecules.

Multiple resin infusion scenarios are possible, each influencing the final properties of the composite. The first scenario is that the CNT yarns contain residual or/and added polymer from their original processing step, like in [2] for example. In this case the yarns themselves would be considered a composite and the infusion of the “secondary” resin would result in no (or very little) penetration inside the CNT yarns. In the second scenario, the epoxy resin has a high enough molecular weight and viscosity for the yarns being partially penetrated by the resin. This is the most complex interface morphology, because mechanical interlocking at the surfaces of the CNTs inside the yarn would be the main load transfer mechanism. In the third scenario, the porous CNT yarns would be completely infiltrated by epoxy resin. This system is more similar to a traditional nanocomposite where there are interactions and load transfer between each CNT or CNT bundle and the matrix.

Although the properties of all three CNT reinforced composite types mentioned above should be considered in the future studies, in order to determine the strengths and weaknesses of each, the dynamic mechanical analysis study (DMA) conducted here assumes that the CNT yarn composites correspond to the third type, where the resin has fully penetrated inside the yarn.

Previously, 3-D braided preforms made from CNT yarns were infused with a low viscosity resin system that had varying mechanical properties with the addition of a mono-epoxide modifier [1]. The mechanical properties of these are summarized in Table 1 with the different composites being distinguished by their Epoxy:Modifier:Hardener ratio. There are very unusual results revealed by the test data, namely that the strain-to-failure values for all four tested composites are about 4 times lower than respective strain-to-failure value for their dry CNT reinforcements, and that those values are much lower than the theoretical (12-25%) [7-9] and measured (4-12%) [10-12] strain-to-failure values for the multi-walled CNTs themselves. Those values are also about twice lower than the strain-to-failure value of unmodified neat epoxy and many times lower than the strain-to-failure values of the other three (modified) epoxies. Indeed, it is hard to explain mechanistically such unusual synergistic effect as strain-to-failure value for a composite is substantially lower than strain-to-failure values for both the matrix and reinforcement. Also, it is highly interesting why the composites made with very different matrices show practically identical strain-to-failure values in the range of 1.6-1.8%. The latter may simply mean that any of these very different matrix

materials in these unusual composites are not allowed to deform in the same manner as it would have occurred in a conventional composite reinforced with the micron scale diameter fibers. DMA is used here to study the relaxation processes (a.k.a. thermal transitions) in the same composites as tested in [1], in order to explain the aforementioned unusual effects.

Table 1. Experimental strength and strain-to-failure data for 3-D braided CNT yarn composites vs. neat resin [1].

Material tested	Strength (MPa)		Strain-to-failure (%)	
	Composite	Neat Resin	Composite	Neat Resin
3-D braid composite 100:0:25	314.8	64.7	1.63	3.6
3-D braid composite 80:20:22	274.2	33.8	1.80	22.5
3-D braid composite 70:30:21	232.0	11.6	1.72	62.0
3-D braid composite 60:40:20	255.4	6.6	1.61	89.3

Figure 1. (a) 3-D braided preform made from thirty six 5-ply CNT yarns. (b) Magnified view of one single yarn making up the preform.

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

DMA is most commonly used by the polymer industry to identify the thermal properties of new polymeric materials, however, the same technique can be used to study composite materials [13,14]. If the composite is reinforced by a fibrous material having stiffness orders of magnitude higher than that of the matrix material, and if the reinforcing material is non-polymeric, then the reinforcement can be considered an ideally elastic element in the composite system. Accordingly, the reinforcement is not supposed to make any contribution to the dampening of the composite system. In such type of composite, the $\tan \delta$ value, or damping, is reduced proportionally to the increase of the volume fraction of fibers. This is simply because as smaller the volume fraction of a viscoelastic matrix constituent in the composite, as lower the composite damping shall be. Very importantly, the temperature at which the $\tan \delta$ peak occurs is not affected by the volume fraction of an elastic reinforcement, because in traditional composites the structure, morphology and properties of the polymer matrix remain the same at all fiber volume fractions. Rigorously, this statement is not absolute, because in the interfacial regions between the fibers and matrix the two constituents may be engaged in some chemical or physical interactions, and those may affect the damping

properties of the composite. However, the proportion of the total volume of such interfacial regions to the total volume of the bulk matrix is so minuscule that such effects would not considerably influence the damping revealed by DMA.

As the size scale of the reinforcing fibers gets smaller, the total percentage of polymer chains interacting with the fibers increases. As the transverse size of fibers approaches the nanoscale of the polymer macromolecules, the large surface area of interaction between the fibers and macromolecules shall reflect in the total intensity of non-elastic interactions, which has to be seen, consequently, in the $\tan \delta$ curves of the composite.

It is worth mentioning in this context that when using nanosized particles, researchers have been able to increase the glass transition temperature, as indicated by the $\tan \delta$ peak obtained from DMA. This effect was reported for the nanoparticle reinforced PVC [15], polyurethane [16] and epoxy [17]. Analogous effects were observed for CNTs dispersed in polymers. A slight decrease in the $\tan \delta$ value with a small increase in glass transition temperature T_g was reported for CNT-epoxy composites with ultra low weight fractions of 0.01-0.05 % of CNTs [18]. When utilizing larger weight fractions, from 0.1 to 0.4%, the authors of [19] showed a progressive decrease in the $\tan \delta$ of their CNT-epoxy composites, as well as a progressive increases in T_g with increasing weight fraction of the CNTs. Carbon nanotubes in polycarbonate showed the same trends with small changes in $\tan \delta$ and T_g temperature peak [20,21]. While the α -transition is most often studied due to its direct relation to the T_g , the β -transition is primarily important when defining the toughness or brittleness of the material. Of the previously mentioned studies, only the authors in [21] tested their samples at temperatures low enough to identify the β -transitions in their CNT-polycarbonate composite, but no effect of the CNTs on this transition was revealed. Data from a DMA study of buckypapers composites showed the most dramatic, among all previously published results, reduction of $\tan \delta$ due to the interaction of the epoxy with the CNTs [22].

EXPERIMENTAL

The composites that were studied in [1] were also utilized in this work, as to allow for establishing correlation between the composites tensile properties on one side and their thermo-mechanical properties on the other. 3-D braided CNT yarn preforms were produced from thirty six 5-ply carbon nanotube yarns [1]. The final braid length was around half of a meter, allowing for multiple tensile and DMA samples to be made from a preform with a constant cross section. As in [1], several formulations of epoxy were used to demonstrate the effect of the epoxy properties on the thermo-mechanical properties. Three Epon 9504 epoxy resin systems, differing in the amount of Heloxy 116 mono-epoxide modifier, were used for the DMA samples. The Heloxy modifier served to lower the mixed viscosity, but unlike a normal solvent it contains a single functional group that bonds to the amine hardener reducing the number of sites for cross-linking. Increasing the amount of the modifier decreases the number of crosslinks in the epoxy which has a profound effect on the mechanical and thermo-mechanical properties. Three formulations were used with Epoxy:Modifier:Hardener ratios of 100:0:25, 80:20:22 and 60:40:20. The original resin system used had a mixed viscosity of approximately 300 cp at room temperature and 60 cp at 60°C. Addition of the modifier further reduced these values. Neat resin samples were fabricated by making a 1 mm thick film on a flat aluminum plate and heating at 60°C in a vacuum oven for 30 minutes. The films were then allowed to cure for 16 hours at room temperature and then

post cured at 90 °C for one hour. The films could then be cut into strips for testing. In order to make the 3-D braided CNT composite samples, the same heating and curing procedure was applied, with one important addition. Namely, after heating the preform was attached to a spring loaded curing apparatus. This device applied approximately 25 grams of force to produce as straight as possible “unidirectional” type composite sample, and to force out excess resin, which was blotted away as tension was increased.

The neat resin samples and the 3-D braided CNT yarn composite samples were studied on a TA Instruments Q800 DMA. The samples were tested in tension with a gauge length of 2 cm, fixed strain of 0.1% and cycling frequency of 1 Hz. Storage modulus, loss modulus, and $\tan \delta$ data were collected from -100 to +150°C. Cross-sectional area was determined by measuring the area of a fractured 3-D braid composite sample using special equipment and software, as described in [1].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Resin Penetration of the CNT Yarns

Infusion of a resin into a densely packed network of CNTs is highly dependent on the molecular shape and size of the resin and hardener molecules, as well as on the viscosity of the mixed system. Fig. 2(a) shows a scanning electron microscope (SEM) image of the surface of a yarn. Empty space or “pores” ranging from 5-50 nm are distinguishable. Polymer chains with a high molecular weight will have a radius of gyration that is larger than most of the pores and, thus, they will be unable to penetrate inside the yarn even if they are dissolved in a very dilute solution with low viscosity. Epoxy resin and hardener molecules are much smaller in size with their longest dimension along the chain axis as low as 2.3 nm [22]. The dimensions in the other two directions are usually less than 1 nm. The viscosity of resin molecules is important even for small diameter molecules; epoxy systems with similar molecular weights can have different viscosities based on their chemistry. If the resin molecules are of sufficiently small size, they are not “filtered” by the CNTs, the time for impregnation for a porous medium can be estimated by solving for time derived from Darcy’s Law [23]:

$$t = \frac{\mu L^2}{kP} \quad (1)$$

where t is the infusion time, μ is the viscosity of resin system, L is the distance for infusion, k is the permeability of the porous medium and P is the pressure. The value for permeability of densely packed CNT buckypapers was measured to be $2 \times 10^{-19} \text{ m}^2$ in [22]. Due to the volume fractions recorded in that study were similar to the ones typical for our CNT yarn composites, it is assumed here that the permeability of CNT yarns would also be similar, and the value $2 \times 10^{-19} \text{ m}^2$ is further used in our estimation.

The individual yarns used to create the 3-D braided CNT composite have an average diameter of 10 μm . Thus, the average distance needed for full infusion was 5 μm from the surface to the core of the yarn. Using a mixed and heated resin viscosity of 100 cp under full vacuum, the estimated time for full infusion was 125 seconds. Even with a large margin of error it is safe to say that this resin system is capable of penetrating the epoxy network before significant network formation and the subsequent increase in chain length and viscosity.

Figure 2. High resolution images of CNT yarn surface before epoxy infusion (a) and the fracture surface of the composite showing good epoxy penetration (b).

Density measurements and high resolution scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images, as seen in Fig. 2(b), confirmed that all three resin systems, having different formulations, have penetrated in between CNTs and/or within their bundles. Due to the high flexibility and low density of the CNT yarns and significant tension applied during curing, many of the yarns changed their cross-sectional shapes from the initially nearly-circular to irregular ones. This allowed them to pack as tightly as possible to each other, resulting in a composite with very few resin-rich areas between the yarns.

Experimental DMA Results and Discussion

The results of the DMA testing of the neat Epon epoxies are shown in Fig. 3(a). This testing was done, primarily, to ensure the proper functionality of the machine and to provide a comparison basis for the other tested materials. The variations of the storage modulus E' and $\tan \delta$ with temperature T follow the trends that are seen in many textbook examples of the DMA studies of epoxy resins. When the mono-epoxide modifier was added to the epoxy, the number of crosslinks was decreased; this is due to the fact that the modifier contains only one functional group. As a result of the lower number of crosslinks, there is some gain in flexibility of large segments in the macromolecular chains. Accordingly, the thermal energy which is required for reaching a larger scale molecular motion is lowered and, thus, the α -transition peak at the T_g moves to a lower temperature and has lower amplitude. The α -transition peak moves to approximately 70°C in the case of 20% modifier and to approximately 50°C in the case of 40% modifier. This means, in particular, that room temperature gets closer to the α -peak location with increasing modifier content. Accordingly, epoxy resin should become “softer” at room temperature with increasing amount of modifier; its modulus has to reduce, and its strain to failure has to increase. In fact, these effects have been observed in our tensile tests of the neat resins.

When the same three resin formulations, characterized by the modifier content 0, 20% and 40%, were used in the fabrication of 3-D braided CNT yarn composites, it was anticipated that the composites would behave as the “mixtures” of two individual constituents, e.g. the multi-walled CNTs, serving as the reinforcement elements, and the epoxy matrix. Specifically, in a system with negligibly low reinforcement dampening, the damping characteristic of the composite can be estimated by the Rule of Mixtures type equation [24]:

$$\tan \delta_c = (1 - V_f) \cdot \tan \delta_m \quad (2)$$

Fig. 3(b) clearly indicates that this is not the case for the three composites studied here. Instead of mimicking the characteristics of these very distinct epoxy matrices, the three $\tan \delta$ curves show very close to each other. Particularly, the variation of T_g value is much lower in Fig. 3(b) than in Fig. 3(a), and the α -peak is not nearly as sharp. The peak values of $\tan \delta$ (between 0.09 and 0.11) in Fig. 3(b) are much lower than those in Fig. 3(a) (between 0.65 and 1.05). Obviously, these experimental values of $\tan \delta$ do not follow the Rule of Mixtures (2). Rather, they are much lower than equation (2) predicts for a conventional, micro-scale fiber reinforcement (if assuming 40% fiber volume fraction in (2), $\tan \delta$ values have to be in the range 0.39-0.63). Therefore, the damping decrease is much lower than expected for the same 40% total volume fraction of carbon nanotubes in the composites.

Figure 3. Experimental storage modulus (green) and $\tan \delta$ curves (red) for neat epoxy resin (a) and 3-D braided composite (b). The amount of modifier in the epoxy and the composites is given by (◆) 0%, (□) 20% and (●) 40%.

Obviously, the penetration of epoxy macromolecules into relatively small spaces between those densely packed CNTs and interaction with them at nano-scale level changes the regular cross-linked epoxy network. With such a close proximity of CNTs to each other, there is significant reduction in the number of chemical cross-links in the epoxy network, which reflects in the shift of T_g toward lower temperatures. At the same time, a much lower thermal energy is required for the α -transition of all three epoxy matrices, when the matrix is spread in relatively small areas among the nanotubes.

Most interestingly, at room temperature all three composites show nearly identical, and very low, values of $\tan \delta$ in the range 0.01-0.015. These values are about 25 times lower than the $\tan \delta$ value for the neat epoxy with 40% modifier, see Fig. 3(a). Now, it becomes obvious that there is a strong correlation between the earlier observed dramatic difference in the strain-to-failure values of the composites and their neat matrices, and the newly revealed $\tan \delta$ values on the other. Specifically, the strain-to-failure values for all four composites, made with resins having different amount of modifier and tested at room temperature, were found very close, see Table 1, This result is in a full correspondence with the new observation that at room temperature the $\tan \delta$ values for those composites are also very close. The result that the strain-to-failure values of all four CNT composites are “abnormally” low, is also in a full correspondence with the result that for all those composites the $\tan \delta$ values are “abnormally” small.

Fig. 3(b) also shows the similarities in DMA curves for the storage modulus of the 3-D braid CNT composites. The curves are very close to each other in the whole temperature range. At room temperature, the storage modulus values were about 30 GPa, which is higher than the respective modulus values (approximately 24 GPa and 19 GPa, see [1]) obtained from the static tensile tests. The discrepancy is reasonable, considering that the dynamic modulus obtained from DMA tests shall be, and usually is, higher than the static one.

It has been shown in [25] that in epoxy networks the macromolecular chain flexibility has a greater importance for the defect nucleation than the density of cross-linking. Therefore, increasing the chain stiffness (or respectively reducing the local mobility of epoxy macromolecules) can increase the rate of the defect initiation and propagation, thus making the material more brittle. As mentioned above, in the nanotube composites studied here, carbon nanotubes occupy about 40% of composite's volume. Hence, they not only affect the cross-linking, but also severely constrain the local motions of epoxy chains spread in the spaces among the nanotubes. Being in a close proximity of carbon nanotubes, severely hinders even smaller, sub-segmental molecular motions which determine the β -transition peak and its location on the temperature axis.

Fig. 4 provides a more detailed comparison of the $\tan \delta$ variations at low temperatures for the three neat epoxy resins and respective three nanotube braid composites. All three curves, corresponding to 0%, 20% and 40% modifier in the epoxy formulation, show much higher $\tan \delta$ values than those seen for the respective three composites. The three curves for respective composites are very close to each other, are located much lower than the neat epoxy curves, and their β -transition peaks are very shallow. This demonstrates again that in the presence of densely packed carbon nanotubes, significant differences in the DMA response, observed for the three neat epoxies, almost disappear.

Figure 4. $\tan \delta$ curves for the epoxy (red) and composite (green) systems. The amount of modifier in the epoxy and the composites is given by (♦) 0%, (□) 20% and (●) 40%.

The DMA data discussed above clearly show that there is a strong effect on the mobility of the epoxy chains in the vicinity of the densely packed network of CNTs within the yarns. This effect, in turn, makes severe impact on the mechanical properties of the nanocomposites. However, this might not be the only mechanism which is operating to cause the more-like-brittle behavior of the composites which are reinforced with a very compliant, ductile matrix. A thermosetting epoxy forms a 3-D “primary” network of chemically crosslinked bonds. A “secondary”, physical in nature crosslinking occurs when chains are trapped in position by their chemically crosslinked neighbours. This is

analogous to two interconnected rings, neither is physically attached but both are incapable of dramatically changing their position in relation to each other. The mechanical properties of a pure resin are much more dependent on the chemical crosslinks than any physical crosslinks that are present. As follows from the results of this work, in nanocomposites with a high volume fraction of CNTs, the physical crosslinking plays a dominant role at room temperature. Indeed, when epoxy resin is infused into the network of CNTs, the nanotubes act as the physical crosslinking agents when the epoxy chains spread among the nanotubes. The CNTs may act as “pinning” the epoxy macromolecules with subsequent restriction of the deformation and initiation of the nano-scale cracks around the CNTs. Owing to a high nanotube volume fraction in CNT yarns, significant portions of the epoxy chains are probably exposed to this pinning effect. We suggest that the combined effect of physical suppression of the local movements in epoxy chains and pinning of the epoxy crosslinks is responsible for the synergistic mechanical behaviour effects first revealed in [1] and further analyzed in this work.

CONCLUSIONS

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis was used here for developing a basic understanding of the interactions of different property epoxy resins with CNTs in 3-D braided CNT yarn composites. The obtained results point to the fact that the nanotubes do, in fact, substantially hinder the local sub-segmental motions of the epoxy macromolecules. This effect is much more pronounced than the effects commonly seen in composites reinforced with dispersed CNTs. This is attributed to a much higher volume fraction of CNTs in the composites studied here. This appears to be a paramount factor to be taken into consideration when determining the mechanical properties of polymer matrix composites reinforced with carbon nanotube yarns, braids, weaves, knits and other possible textiles.

Another important conclusion made from results of this study is that the formulation of epoxy resin (i.e., the amount of modifier added), its viscosity and its DMA properties (expressed via the storage modulus, loss modulus and $\tan \delta$) make rather small effect on the respective DMA properties of the studied composites (in which carbon nanotubes occupy about 40% of the composite's volume). This conclusion is in full agreement with the tensile test data, obtained in [1], that elastic modulus, strength and strain-to-failure of composites reinforced with carbon nanotube yarns and 3-D braids are rather insensitive to the formulation of epoxy resin and its mechanical properties.

These results will influence the design of future CNT yarn or fiber composites. Using other low molecular weight, low viscosity epoxy resins would most likely lead to similar conclusions. Conducting similar experiments with high molecular weight, high viscosity resins, many of which are important to the composites industry, could produce nanocomposites with a variety of very unusual matrix – reinforcement interactions and, consequently, with unconventional mechanical characteristics. These authors believe that experimental results and discussions presented in this work touch the very soul of the future research and development in the area of carbon nanotube composites.

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